

Stress Dealt by English Medium Students doing B.ed

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Abstract:- The purpose of this research is to highlight the problems that have been incurring from the past decade in the South Gujarat Universities, where in students that come from English medium have to go through while studying B. ED courses that are only in Gujarati. Students from English medium go through a lot of difficulty and stress due to the non- availability of English materials and non-availability of English staff. This research will focus on that stress and problems of the students.

Keywords:- STRESS, B. ED, STUDENTS, UNIVERSITIES, SWOT, DEPRESSION.

I. INTRODUCTION

Stress is something that mingles with your head, mingles with your mind and mingles on towards all your thoughts and thought processes throughout your body. Stress isn't a good thing for anyone to incur or on with. Stress completely changes a person from what he or she may actually be. Nowadays stress is not only seen when you are working but in amongst all students up from standard 12 to colleges. Stress has taken up over our lives but what would be more stressful than a student going throughout a very difficult phase of scooping him or herself through the brutal phase of facing oneself from one language to another in a minute second.

Lack of sources for teaching in English have created a lot of stress and created a lot of chaos in a student's life who has almost had their all life gone through an English medium school. Imagine yourself being a throughout English medium student entering a class and the first words of a teacher or the first lines of your teacher go in to Gujarati language and it's all away above your head. That is how a student feels when he or she has to go through when there is lack of English teachers and sources of English teaching in a college. South Gujarat faces a lot of problem in material distribution in English medium in a B. ED department or bachelors of educations department. It's like a visa-versa situation wherein if you have a teacher to teach, then you do not have the material to be taught from and if you have the material to be taught from you do not have the teachers that can teach.

It's almost double and double or triple the efforts you have to put through while going through your notes segregations and notes making rather than what the Gujarati students have to face. Gujarati students have a real advantage as they have Gujarati teachers, Gujarati materials and whole sum lot of Gujarati things that they can

go through with it. It is really sad that south Gujarat universities or colleges have not yet been on a full word of opening a full functioning English medium college for the bachelors of education department (B. ED).

Students suffer through a lot like, lack of confidence, demoralisation, a lot of stress, lot of psychological problems to go through and a feeling of incompetency amongst themselves. This research is not just for the existing students but is in hope for some changes to be made and a better future for the future upcoming of the students pursuing to enrol in bachelors of education (B. ED).

It is a whole sum of tragedy that one has to go through such a lot of pain and suffering only while to do something they love to do. As a result of such a problematic issue there are many a pupil that forfeit to do so. At times it is not the organisation that loses a talent but it is the future generations that may lose a good and great teacher that could have been upcoming to the educational streams and would have been a much greater contribution to the economy and to the Society of India. The procedures, the systems, everything around are so much engrossed an eloped that there is no end to whatever you may seem to struggle to do. It never ends or it never ends in your favour as to you like to do.

Certain times it just seems that you have no other means to do things but to go on with the things that are in front of you making you in so much lot of despair and making you feel so much stressed and burnt out, even frustrated, irritated and ignoring towards your other duties and responsibilities that the system just feels like it's in vain.

This research is not just a problem that has been incurred since the last few years but it has been incurring since the last decade. The problem of students not receiving materials or books or any other subjects in English but only receiving in Gujarati has become a major issue in all of South Gujarat universities. Teachers are forced to be taught in Gujarati when they can even exceptionally teach in English just rather because there is no material to be given in English. Publications have no rights or no materials of their own to publish in English. These are many difficulties that are faced by students for getting materials in English. It is said that a teacher encourages minds to think and to create and hearts to love. But do you think will that teacher be able to give a mind to create if he or she hasn't been given a mind to think before or be groomed enough to teach the future generations.

This research has been held up in the dignity and the degradation for the future teachers to hold up their own personalities and to hold up their own language in which they have been taught since the beginning and they understand well. As for those languages that did not understand it is no shame to be learning new languages but it is more that you understand in which you have been groomed. And brought up since you were a child it is what it is and you need to be firm and stand up with all you got throughout your way.

II. PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEMS

According to CLEVELAND CLINIC [MY.CLEVELANDCLINIC.ORG] “Stress is a normal reaction the body has when changes occur, resulting in physical, emotional and intellectual responses.”

In accordance to this when we take a lot of stress out mind and body get disturbed and result in a lot of changes. Physical changes may lead to:

- Panic attacks
- Headaches.
- Exhaustion
- Trouble sleeping
- Weak immune system
- High/low blood pressure

And stress can also cause the following emotional changes in ones body:

- Anxiety or irritability
- Depression
- Sadness
- Panic attacks
- Mood swings
- A sense of loosing all the confidence

Thus, we can see that stress can cause a lot of problems in one’s life and can impact it a lot. And in the cases of students taking stress, it can cause them all their hard work and the time and efforts they devote in doing what they do.

III. SWOT ANALYSIS

SWOT analysis is a strategic planning and strategic management technique used to help a person or organization to identify Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats related to business competition or project planning. It sometimes called situational assessment or situational analysis. This research presents the SWOT analysis on the stress of students doing B. ED courses. There are a lot of things that can trigger stress and lead to many a conclusions but gathering various data from various students, the below is the SWOT analysis of this research.

IV. REMEDIES

To solve this problem of students getting more and more stressed over studying B. ED in south Gujarat universities we can follow the below remedies. These remedies will not or cannot be changed and implemented all of a sudden in an overnight change, it may and will take some time to change and implement.

R	1. employing more of english medium teaching staff.
E	2. Securing more materials in english for the future generation batches.
M	3. Distribution of authentic materials from universities made by experts to all the colleges.
I	
D	4. Universities need to make more by-lingual syllabus for all.
I	5. Universities need to distribute more reference books that pertain to the syllabus.
E	
S	6. Teachers should make a group with other colleges to obtain notes and reference materials in English for the current students as well as future coming students.

V. CONCLUSION

Through SWOT analysis we can come to know that students not only face problems from the stress that occur while studying B. ED in Gujarati languages but they have also gained a lot of things like self-confidence, increased research capabilities, etc. But we even need to have a look on the other side of the coin that is the problems and the stress that they face like going into major depression, projection of mental illness, issues in translations of notes, lack of time to make notes etc.

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